

Novel Fractional Integral Inequalities of Bullen-Mercer Type Pertaining to Differentiable Convex Functions with Applications

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Article Info

Oral Presentation

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14316560

Keywords

Bullen-Mercer inequality
Convex function
Hölder's inequality
Lipschitz function
Numerical analysis
Young's inequality

Abstract

In this paper, we derive a new Bullen-Mercer type fractional integral identity for differentiable function. By using this identity and many well-known inequalities as auxiliary tools, some novel Bullen-Mercer type inequalities for differentiable convex functions are obtained. Furthermore, from our main results we discuss several important special cases. Moreover, we offer Bullen-Mercer type inequalities pertaining to Lipschitz and bounded functions. Finally, applications to the error bounds, q-digamma function and modified Bessel function are given.

1. Introduction

Convexity theory is a fundamental concept in mathematical analysis that plays a crucial role in various fields, including optimization, economics, and geometry. It provides a powerful framework for studying and analyzing functions and their properties. In particular, convex functions possess significant characteristics that make them exceptionally useful in many applications. Numerical integration formulas and their corresponding error bounds via different techniques have been investigated by many researchers. For instance, in [1, 2], some error bounds have been established for the midpoint and trapezoidal inequalities of numerical integration applying convex functions. The error bounds of Simpson-type inequalities have been established utilizing the convex functions and some of these bounds can be found in [3-5]. The [6] presents Simpson-type inequalities and their application to quadrature inequalities in numerical analysis. A number of fractional Simpson-type inequalities are examined in [7] for the case of functions whose second derivatives in absolute value are convex. Moreover, in [8], several variants of Simpson-type inequalities are studied for the case of differentiable convex functions by generalized fractional integrals. The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule is followed by Simpson's second rule, which is why evaluations involving three-step quadratic kernels are frequently referred to as Newton-type results. The literature refers to these outcomes as Newton-type inequalities. In [9, 10], some error bounds for Newton-type inequalities in numerical integration have also been proved by using the convex functions. For the case of functions whose first

derivative in absolute value at a given power is arithmetically-harmonically convex, various Newton-type inequalities are investigated in [11]. Likewise, certain Newton-type inequalities based on convexity are presented and some applications for special cases of real functions are also given in [12]. Several new estimates of Milne's quadrature rule are obtained in [13]. Moreover, in papers [14,15], fractional versions of Milne-type inequalities are established by using the differentiable convex functions.

The remaining paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we will recall few basic concepts. In Section 3, we will be established an essential identity of fractional Bullen-Mercer type for differentiable function. By using this identity and many well-known inequalities as auxiliary tools, some novel Bullen-Mercer type inequalities for differentiable convex functions will be obtain. Furthermore, from our main results we will discuss several important special cases. Moreover, we offer Bullen-Mercer type inequalities pertaining to Lipschitz and bounded functions. In Section 4, we will present some applications to the error bounds, q-digamma and modified Bessel functions. Finally, some conclusions and future research will be given in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

Let's introduce some primary concepts that will be used in the following sections.

(i) The following is the expression for Simpson's quadrature formula, also referred to as Simpson's 1/3 rule:

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$$\int_a^b F(x)dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[F(a) + 4F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right]$$

(ii) The definition of Simpson's second formula, also referred to as the Newton-Cotes quadratic formula or Simpson's 3/8 rule (see [16]), is as follows:

$$\int_a^b F(x)dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[F(a) + 3F\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + F(b) \right].$$

The following is one of the most famous Newton-Cotes quadrature techniques that uses a three-point Simpson-type inequality:

Theorem 1. Suppose that $F: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|F^{(4)}\|_\infty := \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |F^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[F(a) + 4F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b F(x)dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|F^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

One of the classical closed-type quadrature rules is the Simpson 3/8 rule, which is founded on the Simpson 3/8 inequality, expressed as follows:

Theorem 2. Assume that $F: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|F^{(4)}\|_\infty := \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |F^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[F(a) + 3F\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3F\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b F(x)dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|F^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

The well-known Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals are defined as follows:

Definition 1 ([17,18]). The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a^+}^\alpha F$ and $J_b^- F$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are given by

$$J_{a^+}^\alpha F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-\xi)^{\alpha-1} F(\xi) d\xi, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_b^- F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (\xi-x)^{\alpha-1} F(\xi) d\xi, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. For $\alpha = 1$, we obtain the classical integral. Here, F belongs to $L_1[a, b]$ (the set of all Lebesgue integrable functions on $[a, b]$) and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the well-known Gamma function defining as

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-\xi} \xi^{\alpha-1} d\xi.$$

At the end of this section let us recall the definition of convex function which will be used in the sequel.

Definition 2 ([19,20]). The function $F: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex on I , if

$$F(\xi a + (1-\xi)b) \leq \xi F(a) + (1-\xi) F(b)$$

holds for all $a, b \in [0, \infty[$ and $\xi \in [0, 1]$.

Now we present another famous result due to Jensen, which generalizes the idea of convex functions and is described in [21] as: Suppose F is a convex function defined on $[\rho_1, \rho_2]$, then for any $\delta_i \in [\rho_1, \rho_2]$ and $\mu_i \in [0, 1]$, with $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and $\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i = 1$, the following inequality holds:

$$F\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \delta_i\right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i F(\delta_i).$$

For more details, see [22].

In 2004, Mercer [23] established an improved version of Jensen's inequality which is described as follows:

If $F: [\rho_1, \rho_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function and $\rho_1 < a < b < \rho_2$, then the following inequality holds:

$$F\left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \delta_i\right) \leq F(\rho_1) + F(\rho_2) - \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i F(\delta_i).$$

Integral inequalities are considered from numerous perspectives, but one of its areas is linked with error estimations of commonly studied quadrature and cubature rules.

In [24] Bullen explored another Hermite-Hadamard type inequality, which is regarded as Bullen's inequality. Assume that $F: [\rho_1, \rho_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function, then

$$\frac{1}{\rho_2 - \rho_1} \int_{\rho_1}^{\rho_2} F(\xi) d\xi \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[F\left(\frac{\rho_1 + \rho_2}{2}\right) + \frac{F(\rho_1) + F(\rho_2)}{2} \right].$$

In recent many notable developments regarding this inequality have been established in the literature. This inequality provides the error bounds for the remainder of Bullen quadrature schemes. The main purpose of investigating such types of inequalities is to predict more accurate and strong bounds of error terms.

The main motivation of this paper is that we will establish some new Bullen's type inequalities involving the idea of Jensen-Mercer inequality using fractional calculus for differentiable convex functions and some novel applications to numerical analysis and special functions. To achieve our desired outcomes, we have divided our remaining study into three sections. In the first section, we will establish a new generic Bullen-Mercer type fractional integral identity for the case of differentiable functions. By utilizing this identity as an auxiliary result and the well-known Hölder's, power-mean, and Young's type inequalities some novel Bullen-Mercer type inequalities for differentiable convex functions will be given. Several special cases from our main results will be discuss in detail. In the second section, we will offer Bullen-Mercer type inequalities via Lipschitz and bounded functions. In the last section, some applications to the error

bounds, q-digamma function and modified Bessel function will be obtain.

3. Main Results

In this section, before giving our main results, we need to prove the following crucial lemma.

Lemma 1. Assume that $F: [\rho_1, \rho_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be differentiable function over (ρ_1, ρ_2) with $\rho_1 < a < b < \rho_2$, then

$$I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b) := \frac{(b-a)}{8} \times \left\{ \int_0^1 (1-2\xi^\alpha) F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) d\xi + \int_0^1 (2\xi^\alpha - 1) F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) d\xi \right\},$$

where

$$I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{(\rho_1+\rho_2-b)^+}^\alpha F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) + J_{(\rho_1+\rho_2-a)^-}^\alpha F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right]$$

Proof. By utilizing integration by parts, we can easily obtain the above identity. We omit here the proof.

Remark 1. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Lemma 1, we can obtain the following identity involving classical Riemann integrals:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1+\rho_2-b}^{\rho_1+\rho_2-a} F(\xi) d\xi \right] = \frac{(b-a)}{8} \times \left\{ \int_0^1 (1-2\xi) F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) d\xi + \int_0^1 (2\xi - 1) F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) d\xi \right\}.$$

Using Lemma 1, we are ready to prove the following main results.

Theorem 3. Let us consider that all assumptions of the Lemma 1 hold and $|F'|^q$ is convex function, where $q > 1$ and $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then the following inequality yields:

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} S^{1/p}(p, \alpha) \times \left[\left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{|F'(a)|^q + 3|F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{3|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right],$$

where

$$S(p, \alpha) := \int_0^1 |1 - 2\xi^\alpha|^p d\xi = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \left[\int_{1-2^{1-\alpha}}^1 \xi^p (1-\xi)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} d\xi + \int_{2^{1-\alpha}-1}^1 \xi^p (1+\xi)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} d\xi \right].$$

Proof. From Lemma 1, convexity of $|F'|^q$, Hölder's inequality and properties of the modulus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \int_0^1 |1 - 2\xi^\alpha| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) \right| d\xi + \int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) \right| d\xi \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left[\left(\int_0^1 |1 - 2\xi^\alpha|^p d\xi \right)^{1/p} \times \left(\int_0^1 \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{1/q} + \left(\int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1|^p d\xi \right)^{1/p} \times \left(\int_0^1 \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{1/q} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} S^{1/p}(p, \alpha) \times \left[\left(\int_0^1 \left[|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \left(\frac{1-\xi}{2} \right) |F'(a)|^q + \left(\frac{1+\xi}{2} \right) |F'(b)|^q \right] d\xi \right)^{1/q} + \left(\int_0^1 \left[|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \left(\frac{1+\xi}{2} \right) |F'(a)|^q + \left(\frac{1-\xi}{2} \right) |F'(b)|^q \right] d\xi \right)^{1/q} \right] \\ & = \frac{(b-a)}{8} S^{1/p}(p, \alpha) \times \left[\left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{|F'(a)|^q + 3|F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{3|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 3. ■

Corollary 1. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1+\rho_2-b}^{\rho_1+\rho_2-a} F(\xi) d\xi \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \right)^{1/p} \times \left[\left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{|F'(a)|^q + 3|F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \frac{3|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2. Choosing $|F'| \leq K$ in Theorem 3, we get

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{K(b-a)}{4} S^{1/p}(p, \alpha).$$

Theorem 4. Let us consider that all assumptions of the Lemma 1 hold and $|F'|^q$ is convex function, where $q \geq 1$. Then the following inequality yields:

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} B_3^{1-1/q}(\alpha) \times \left[\left(\frac{|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q}{2} B_3(\alpha) - \frac{|F'(a)|^q B_1(\alpha) + |F'(b)|^q B_2(\alpha)}{2} \right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q}{2} B_3(\alpha) - \frac{|F'(a)|^q B_2(\alpha) + |F'(b)|^q B_1(\alpha)}{2} \right)^{1/q} \right],$$

where

$$B_1(\alpha) := \int_0^1 (1-\xi)|1-2\xi^\alpha| d\xi = \frac{2}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}} - 1 \right) + B_3(\alpha) + \frac{1}{4},$$

$$B_2(\alpha) := \int_0^1 (1+\xi)|1-2\xi^\alpha| d\xi = \frac{2}{\alpha+2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}} \right) + B_3(\alpha) - \frac{1}{4}$$

and

$$B_3(\alpha) := \int_0^1 |1-2\xi^\alpha| d\xi = \frac{2}{\alpha+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^\alpha} \right).$$

Proof. From Lemma 1, convexity of $|F'|^q$, power-mean inequality and properties of the modulus, we have

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \int_0^1 |1-2\xi^\alpha| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) \right| d\xi + \int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) \right| d\xi \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left(\int_0^1 |1-2\xi^\alpha| d\xi \right)^{1-1/q} \\ & \times \left(\int_0^1 |1-2\xi^\alpha| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1-\xi}{2}a - \frac{1+\xi}{2}b \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{1/q} \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1| d\xi \right)^{1-1/q} \\ & \times \left(\int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1| \left| F' \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{1+\xi}{2}a - \frac{1-\xi}{2}b \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned} \right\} \leq \frac{b-a}{4} B_3^{1-1/q}(\alpha) \times \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left(\int_0^1 |1-2\xi^\alpha| \left[|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \left(\frac{1-\xi}{2} \right) |F'(a)|^q + \left(\frac{1+\xi}{2} \right) |F'(b)|^q \right] d\xi \right)^{1/q} \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 |2\xi^\alpha - 1| \left[|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q - \left(\frac{1+\xi}{2} \right) |F'(a)|^q + \left(\frac{1-\xi}{2} \right) |F'(b)|^q \right] d\xi \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 4. ■

Corollary 3. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b}^{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a} F(\xi) d\xi \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-1/q} \times \left[\left(\frac{|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q}{4} - \frac{|F'(a)|^q + 3|F'(b)|^q}{8} \right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q}{4} - \frac{3|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q}{8} \right)^{1/q} \right].$$

Corollary 4. Taking $|F'| \leq K$ in Theorem 4, we obtain

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{K(b-a)}{4} B_3^{1-1/q}(\alpha) \times \left(2B_3(\alpha) - \frac{B_1(\alpha) + B_2(\alpha)}{2} \right)^{1/q}.$$

Theorem 5. Let us consider that all assumptions of the Lemma 1 hold and $|F'|^q$ is convex function, where $q > 1$ and $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then the following inequality yields:

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left[\frac{2}{p} S(p, \alpha) + \frac{2(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q) - (|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q)}{q} \right],$$

where $S(p, \alpha)$ is defined as in Theorem 3.

Proof. From Lemma 1, convexity of $|F'|^q$, Young's inequality and properties of the modulus, we obtain the desired result.

Corollary 5. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 5, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b}^{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a} F(\xi) d\xi \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left[\frac{2}{p(p+1)} + \frac{2(|F'(\rho_1)|^q + |F'(\rho_2)|^q) - (|F'(a)|^q + |F'(b)|^q)}{q} \right].$$

Corollary 6. Taking $|F'| \leq K$ in Theorem 5, we obtain

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{4} \left[\frac{S(p, \alpha)}{p} + \frac{K^q}{q} \right].$$

Theorem 6. Assume that $F: [\rho_1, \rho_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a Lipschitz function with $L > 0$, then the following inequality yields:

$$|I_F^{(\alpha)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{L(b-a)^2}{8} B_4(\alpha),$$

where

$$B_4(\alpha) := \int_0^1 \xi |1-2\xi^\alpha| d\xi = \frac{2}{\alpha+2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}} \right) - \frac{1}{4}.$$

Proof. From Lemma 1, Lipschitz condition of $|F|$ with $L > 0$ and properties of the modulus, we obtain the desired result.

Corollary 7. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 6, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b}^{\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a} F(\xi) d\xi \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{L(b-a)^2}{32}.$$

Theorem 7. Let us consider that all assumptions of the Lemma 1 hold. If there exist constants $-\infty < m < M < +\infty$ such that $m \leq F'(\tau) \leq M, \forall \tau \in [\rho_1, \rho_2]$, then the following inequality yields:

$$|I_F^{(\omega)}(\rho_1, \rho_2, a, b)| \leq \frac{(b-a)(M-m)}{8} B_3(\alpha),$$

where $B_3(\alpha)$ is defined as in Theorem 4.

Proof. From Lemma 1, the assumption that $m \leq F'(\tau) \leq M, \forall \tau \in [\rho_1, \rho_2]$, and properties of the modulus, we obtain the desired result.

Corollary 8. Taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 7, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + F(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + F\left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_{\rho_1}^{\rho_2} F(\xi) d\xi \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)(M-m)}{16}.$$

4. Applications

In the final section, we provide some applications of our main results to the error bounds, modified Bessel function and q-digamma function.

4.1. Modified Bessel functions

The modified Bessel function of the first kind, denoted as $K_\rho(a)$, is a mathematical function defined as the following infinite sum:

$$K_\rho(a) := \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\left(\frac{a}{2}\right)^{\rho+2n}}{n! \Gamma(n + \rho + 1)},$$

where $a > 0$ is a real number and $\rho > -1$.

The modified Bessel function of the second kind, denoted as $B_\rho(a)$, is defined in terms of $K_\rho(a)$ as follows:

$$B_\rho(a) := \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{K_{-\rho}(a) - K_\rho(a)}{\sin(\rho\pi)}.$$

Another function $J_\rho(a)$, can be defined as:

$$J_\rho(a) := 2^\rho \Gamma(\rho + 1) a^{-\rho} B_\rho(a),$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ represents the gamma function.

In the cited reference [25], two derivative formulas for $J_\rho(a)$ are given. The first derivative is expressed as:

$$J'_\rho(a) := \frac{a}{2(\rho + 1)} J_{\rho+1}(a).$$

The second derivative is given by:

$$J''_\rho(a) := \frac{a^2}{4(\rho + 1)(\rho + 2)} J_{\rho+2}(a) + \frac{1}{2(\rho + 1)} J_{\rho+1}(a).$$

Proposition 1. Applying Corollary 1, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) \cdot J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + (\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b) \cdot J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{4(\rho + 1)} + \frac{(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2})}{2(\rho + 1)} \cdot J_{\rho+1}\left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - \frac{J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) - J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{b-a} \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{\rho+1}\right)^{1/p}$$

$$\times \left[\left(\left| \frac{\rho_1^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_1) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\rho_2^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_2) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_2) \right|^q + \frac{\left| \frac{a^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(a) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(a) \right|^q + 3 \left| \frac{b^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(b) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(b) \right|^q \right)^{1/4} + \left(\left| \frac{\rho_1^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_1) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\rho_2^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_2) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_2) \right|^q + 3 \left| \frac{a^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(a) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(a) \right|^q + \left| \frac{b^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(b) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(b) \right|^q \right)^{1/4} \right]$$

Proof. By utilizing Corollary 1 and taking the function $F(a) := J'_\rho(a)$ with $a > 0$, we derive the above inequality.

Proposition 2. Using Corollary 4, we get

$$\left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) \cdot J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + (\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b) \cdot J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{4(\rho + 1)} + \frac{(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2})}{2(\rho + 1)} \cdot J_{\rho+1}\left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - \frac{J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) - J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{b-a} \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{1-1/q} \times \left[\left(\left| \frac{\rho_1^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_1) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\rho_2^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_2) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_2) \right|^q + \frac{\left| \frac{a^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(a) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(a) \right|^q + 3 \left| \frac{b^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(b) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(b) \right|^q \right)^{1/4} + \left(\left| \frac{\rho_1^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_1) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\rho_2^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(\rho_2) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(\rho_2) \right|^q + 3 \left| \frac{a^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(a) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(a) \right|^q + \left| \frac{b^2}{4(\rho+1)(\rho+2)} J_{\rho+2}(b) + \frac{1}{2(\rho+1)} J_{\rho+1}(b) \right|^q \right)^{1/4} \right]$$

Proof. By applying Corollary 4 and choosing the function $F(a) := J'_\rho(a)$ with $a > 0$, we obtain the above result.

4.2. q-Digamma function

The q-digamma function, denoted as \mathfrak{q}_q , is a function that serves as the q-analogue of the digamma function \mathfrak{q} . The formula for \mathfrak{q}_q is provided in the references [25,26] and is given as follows:

$$\mathfrak{q}_q(\gamma) := -\ln(1-q) + \ln q \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{k+\gamma}}{1-q^{k+\gamma}}$$

or alternatively,

$$\mathfrak{q}_q(\gamma) := -\ln(1-q) + \ln q \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{k\gamma}}{1-q^{k\gamma}}$$

This expression holds true when $q > 1$ and $\gamma > 0$. The q-digamma function \mathfrak{q}_q can also be expressed in the following form:

$$\mathfrak{q}_q(\gamma) := -\ln(q-1) + \ln q \left[\gamma - \frac{1}{2} - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{-(k+\gamma)}}{1-q^{-(k+\gamma)}} \right]$$

or alternatively,

$$e_q(\gamma) := -\ln(q-1) + \ln q \left[\gamma - \frac{1}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{-k\gamma}}{1-q^{-k\gamma}} \right].$$

Proposition 3. Applying Corollary 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + q'_q \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) - q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{b-a} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \right)^{1/p} \\ & \times \left[\left(\left| q''_q(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(\rho_2) \right|^q - \frac{\left| q''_q(a) \right|^q + 3 \left| q''_q(b) \right|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\left| q''_q(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(\rho_2) \right|^q \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{3 \left| q''_q(a) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(b) \right|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By utilizing Corollary 1 and taking the function $F(a) := q'_q(a)$, which is completely monotone function on the interval $]0, \infty[$ for all $a > 0$, then $F(a) := q'_q(a)$ is a convex function, and so we derive the above inequality.

Proposition 4. Using Corollary 4, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) + q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{2} + q'_q \left(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - a) - q'_q(\rho_1 + \rho_2 - b)}{b-a} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)}{8} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-1/q} \\ & \times \left[\left(\frac{\left| q''_q(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(\rho_2) \right|^q}{4} - \frac{\left| q''_q(a) \right|^q + 3 \left| q''_q(b) \right|^q}{8} \right)^{1/q} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{\left| q''_q(\rho_1) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(\rho_2) \right|^q}{4} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{3 \left| q''_q(a) \right|^q + \left| q''_q(b) \right|^q}{8} \right)^{1/q} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By utilizing Corollary 4 and choosing the function $F(a) := q'_q(a)$, which is completely monotone function on the interval $]0, \infty[$ for all $a > 0$, then $F(a) := q'_q(a)$ is a convex function, and so we obtain the above result.

4.3. Error bounds

This subsequent part is devoted to establishing some new error bounds of Bullen-type quadrature schemes.

Consider a partition $P: \rho_1 = \tau_0 < \tau_1 < \tau_2 \dots < \tau_i < \tau_{i+1} \dots \tau_n = \rho_2$ of the interval $[\rho_1, \rho_2]$, where $[\tau_i, \tau_{i+1}]$ is any arbitrary subset of $[\rho_1, \rho_2]$.

$$T(P, F) := \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\tau_{i+1} - \tau_i)^2}{2} \left[\frac{F(\tau_i) + F(\tau_{i+1})}{2} + F \left(\frac{\tau_i + \tau_{i+1}}{2} \right) \right];$$

$$\int_{\rho_1}^{\rho_2} F(\xi) d\xi = T(P, F) + R(P, F),$$

where $R(P, F)$ is the error terms.

Proposition 5. From Corollary 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |R(P, F)| & \leq \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \right)^{1/p} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\tau_{i+1} - \tau_i)^2}{8} \\ & \times \left[\left(\left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q - \frac{\left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + 3 \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \frac{3 \left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By utilizing Corollary 1 and setting $a = \rho_1, b = \rho_2$, and then implementing this result over subinterval $[\tau_i, \tau_{i+1}]$, we obtain the above result.

Proposition 6. From Corollary 4, we get

$$|R(P, F)| \leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1/q} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\tau_{i+1} - \tau_i)^2}{8} \left(\frac{\left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q}{8} \right)^{1/q}.$$

Proof. By applying Corollary 4 and letting $a = \rho_1, b = \rho_2$, and then implementing this result over subinterval $[\tau_i, \tau_{i+1}]$, we deduce the above result.

Proposition 7. From Corollary 5, we get

$$|R(P, F)| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\tau_{i+1} - \tau_i)^2}{8} \left[\frac{2}{p(p+1)} + \frac{\left| F'(\tau_i) \right|^q + \left| F'(\tau_{i+1}) \right|^q}{q} \right].$$

Proof. By utilizing Corollary 5 and choosing $a = \rho_1, b = \rho_2$, and then implementing this result over subinterval $[\tau_i, \tau_{i+1}]$, we have the above result.

5. Conclusions

In our study, we established a new generic Bullen-Mercer type fractional integral identity for the case of differentiable functions. By utilizing this identity as an auxiliary result and the well-known Hölder's, power-mean, and Young's type inequalities some novel Bullen-Mercer type inequalities for differentiable convex functions are given. Several special cases from our main results are discussed in detail. Furthermore, we offer Bullen-Mercer type inequalities via Lipschitz and bounded functions. Finally, applications to the error bounds, q-digamma function and modified Bessel function are presented. For future research, interested readers may consider refinements and generalizations of our results by exploring different classes of convex functions for different types of fractional integral operators. We believe that our results can be extend in quantum and post quantum calculus.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The authors of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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